

A Narrative of Monks: Culture Heroes in Songkhla Province

Authors : Kuntalee Vaitayavanich

Abstract : This study aimed to look into roles of culture heroes of monks in Buddhism in Songkhla province during the last 50 years. Qualitative study, in-depth interviews, participatory observation and non-participatory observation were employed for this study. The results of the study indicated that culture heroes in Songkhla province would act as the followings. 1) For secular matters, monks would do something beneficial to the community. 2) For religious matters, monks would behave to follow Buddhism discipline strictly and unambitiously. At the same time, monks would not neglect to teach Buddhists to give respect to Lord Buddha by doing meditation and praying. However, when some of those culture heroes passed away, villagers in the community would show gratitude and appreciation by arranging a religious death anniversary ceremony, having icon, or having narrative to recognize those, continuously.

Keywords : narrative of monks, culture heroes, Songkhla province, social sustainability

Conference Title : ICECESS 2014 : International Conference on Environmental, Cultural, Economic and Social Sustainability

Conference Location : Venice, Italy

Conference Dates : April 14-15, 2014